

OPTIMISATION OF IN-PLANE AND BENDING PROPERTIES OF WOVEN FABRIC LAMINATE CONFIGURATIONS

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SUMMARY: The properties of a satin weave glass/carbon hybrid composite lamina are established according to the theory in [1-3]. This is extended to a multi-layered solution where the main focus is on the behaviour of 3-layered symmetric laminates. Various angular orientations are imparted to each layer according to the standard transformation equations [4]. Vertical shifts are allocated to each layer to fix its position in the lay-up. Once the describing matrices have been determined, the deflection characteristics of a simply supported rectangular plate can be found according to [5,6]. Through changing the thickness and geometry of the various layers, changes to the angle of the various laminae and of the whole plate to the simple supports, the influence of each of the parameters on the plate deflection can be determined. It is also possible to show an optimal solution for minimum deflection of the plate.

KEYWORDS: woven fabric, deflection, in-plane, satin weave

INTRODUCTION

The properties of a satin weave glass/carbon hybrid composite lamina are established according to the theory in [1-3]. The in-plane properties predicted by the parallel-series scheme in [1] have been shown to agree well with experimental data. The investigation is extended here to include bending properties. It has been found, although not presented here, that there is a significant difference between the results obtained ignoring weave structures and those obtained considering them. The focus of this study is therefore to investigate the influence of weave structure on the deflection of a plate.

In order to extend the theory to a laminated plate, the summation of the various matrices that describe each lamina is done at the end of the unit cells. It is therefore possible to change the angular orientation of each layer, which could not be achieved previously. The in-plane properties of each constituent layer are determined to show the influence of this on the behaviour of the laminate. It will be shown that although the in-plane properties are not used directly for the determination of deflection characteristics, these properties are closely related.

THEORY

Material Properties

The material properties of each woven fabric lamina were first established. This involved defining shape functions for the weave structure. These shape functions can be found in [1-3].

The relevant stiffness parameters could be found as presented in [1], [3]. Relevant dimensions and terms can be seen in Fig. 1.

The satin weave under consideration consists of carbon fibre reinforcement in the *Warp* direction and glass fibre reinforcement in the *Fill* direction. The assumed properties of the carbon, glass and resin are presented in Table 1.

Fig. 1: Unit cell of weave structure and relevant dimensions

Model Details

The weave under consideration was a satin weave where the thickness $h^{(k)} / a_w^{(k)}$ could be varied. It was assumed that the gap between adjacent yarns is so small that it is insignificant. A three-layer laminate configuration (Fig. 2) was assumed and the overall thickness of this laminate was kept constant. The proportionate thickness of each of the component layers was, however, varied. It was assumed that the two outer laminae were identical in terms of thickness and orientation. For the middle layer (here termed layer 1), $h^{(1)}$ was varied while $a_w^{(1)}$ was kept constant. This changed the ratio $h^{(1)} / a_w^{(1)}$, which changed the shape of the weave and hence affected the properties. For the outer layers (each termed layer 2), $h^{(2)} / a_w^{(2)}$ was kept constant as the value of $h^{(2)}$ was varied. The properties of the outer layers thus remained constant and were subject only to variation under off-axis loading.

The properties of the outer layers were kept constant throughout the investigation in order to establish how the weave structure of the middle layer would affect the behaviour of the laminated plate, particularly under bending loads.

Table 1: Constituent material properties

	E_L	E_T	G_{LT}	G_{TT}	ν_{LT}
Glass	71.5	71.5	27.5	27.5	0.29
Carbon	210.0	39.6	24.0	14.3	0.26
Resin	3.5	3.5	1.3	1.3	0.35

Fig. 2: Stacking of unit cells for determination of stiffness parameters

Stiffness Parameters

Finding the bending resistance of each layer involves finding the elements of the D-matrix. The following relationship from [7] is commonly used to describe the behaviour of a plate where material and geometric nonlinearities are small:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \{N\} \\ \{M\} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} [A] & [B] \\ [B] & [D] \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \{\varepsilon^0\} \\ \{\kappa\} \end{Bmatrix} \quad [\text{none}] \quad (1)$$

where [A] gives the in-plane stiffness, [D] the coupling stiffness and [B] gives the coupling terms of the stiffness matrix. $\{N\}$, $\{\varepsilon^0\}$ are in-plane forces and mid-surface strains respectively and $\{M\}$, $\{\kappa\}$ are bending moments and curvatures respectively. It shall be shown later that we do not need to find the elements of the [B] matrix. The in-plane stiffness matrix [A] can be found from:

$$\begin{aligned} A^{(k)}(x, y) = & Q^M [hx_3^{(k)}(x, y) + h_u^{(k)} - h_l^{(k)} - hx_2^{(k)}(x, y)] \\ & + Q^W(x, y)[hx_2^{(k)}(x, y) - hx_1^{(k)}(x, y)] \\ & + Q^F(x, y)[hx_1^{(k)}(x, y) - hx_3^{(k)}(x, y)] \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

and the bending stiffness from:

$$\begin{aligned}
 D^{(k)}(x, y) = & Q^M [hx_3^{(k)}(x, y)^3 - (h_u^{(k)} / 2)^3 + (h_l^{(k)} / 2)^3 + hx_2^{(k)}(x, y)^3] \\
 & + Q^W(x, y)[hx_2^{(k)}(x, y)^3 - hx_1^{(k)}(x, y)^3] \\
 & + Q^F(x, y)[hx_1^{(k)}(x, y)^3 - hx_3^{(k)}(x, y)^3]
 \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

where Q^M , $Q^W(x, y)$, $Q^F(x, y)$ are the Q matrices of the *Matrix*, *Fill* and *Warp* yarns respectively; and $h_u^{(k)}$ and $h_l^{(k)}$ are the upper and lower limits of the lamina, the extreme points of its thickness $h^{(k)}$.

In order to account for the different angular orientation of each layer, the matrices for each are transformed according to the standard orthotropic transformation equations given in [4]. The transformed matrices are simply added together to find the overall matrices for the laminate. It can be shown that if the laminate is symmetrical, the terms of the $[B]$ matrix cancel when this addition is made, leaving no coupling between bending and in-plane forces. This simplifies the investigation significantly.

It is assumed, as in [5], that the applied load on the plate at is given by:

$$q = \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} q_{mn} \cos \frac{m\pi x}{a} \sin \frac{n\pi y}{b} \tag{4}$$

A rectangular plate, simply supported at the edges, is the focus of this study. In order to apply simply supported boundary conditions to the plate boundaries shown in Fig. 3, the following expressions apply:

For $x = 0, a$

$$w = 0, M_x = B_{16} \left(\frac{\partial u^0}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v^0}{\partial x} \right) - D_{11} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} - D_{12} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} = 0 \tag{5}$$

$$u^0 = 0, N_{xy} = A_{66} \left(\frac{\partial u^0}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v^0}{\partial x} \right) - B_{16} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} - B_{26} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} = 0 \tag{6}$$

For $y = 0, b$

$$w = 0, M_y = B_{26} \left(\frac{\partial u^0}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v^0}{\partial x} \right) - D_{12} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} - D_{22} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} = 0 \tag{7}$$

$$v^0 = 0, N_{xy} = 0 \tag{8}$$

Fig. 3. Laminated plate dimensions

The deflection at each point on the plate is then given by the expression:

$$w(x, y) = \frac{R^4 b^4}{\pi^4} \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} q_{mn} \frac{\sin \frac{m\pi x}{a} \sin \frac{n\pi y}{b}}{[D_{11}m^4 + 2(D_{12} + 2D_{66})m^2 n^2 R^2 + D_{22}n^4 R^4]} \quad (9)$$

where the maximum deflection will occur in the centre of the plate for a uniformly distributed load. From [6], it can be seen that $m = 1, 3, 5, \dots$ and $n = 1, 3, 5, \dots$. The series achieves rapid convergence and it in practice m and n were summed to 99, which yields a very small error in the results. The plate is assumed to be square for the purposes of the investigation. This means that the value of the aspect ratio R in equation (8) is 1.

The properties of the each of the layers and the overall plate model as entered for computation by the model are as follows:

- Plain satin weave, $a_w^{(k)} = a_f^{(k)}$
- Undulation, $u^{(k)} / a_w^{(k)} = 0.6$
- Fibre volume content = 0.6
- Size of plate $a / a_w^{(1)} = 100.0$ and $b / b_w^{(1)} = 100.0$.

RESULTS

The maximum deflection for a layer of core material with $h^{(1)} / a_w^{(1)} = 1.0$ and with infinitely thin outer layers is given in Fig. 4a. It can be seen that there is considerable variation in the maximum deflection as the orientation of the plate is altered. The maximum deflection is $w / h = 0.26 \times 10^{-3}$ and occurs when the 0/45/0 laminate is orientated at 90° to the simple supported boundary of the plate. Note that $h = h^{(1)} + 2h^{(2)}$. The configuration with the lowest variation is the 0/0/0 laminate. The maximum deflection occurs at a load angle of 60° , which is a feature repeated in later results.

The maximum deflection of a plate with $h^{(1)} / a_w^{(1)} = 0.9$ can be seen to be $w/a = 0.17 \times 10^{-3}$ from Fig. 2b. This occurs in the 0/60/0 laminate for an orientation angle of 75° . The variation in the behaviour of the different configurations is substantially reduced.

Fig. 2c displays an interesting occurrence. All the laminate configurations begin to display a similar pattern for maximum deflection when $h^{(1)} / a_w^{(1)} = 0.7$. In almost all cases max. $w/a = 0.14 \times 10^{-3}$ at an orientation angle of 60° . It is clear from this point on that the middle layer (layer 1) does not influence the behaviour of the laminate significantly when $h^{(1)} / a_w^{(1)} \leq 0.7$. Only the magnitude of deflection is affected by the ratio of middle layer thickness to overall thickness.

It is found that under the conditions chosen here, the minimum deflection is achieved when $h^{(1)} / a_w^{(1)} = 0.5$. For this case, maximum $w/a = 0.125 \times 10^{-3}$ at an orientation angle between 45° and 60° for almost any laminate configuration.

Fig. 4a: Max. $w/h \times 10^3$ for plate with $h^{(1)} / a_w^{(1)} = 1.0$

Fig. 4b: Max. $w/h \times 10^3$ for plate with $h^{(1)} / a_w^{(1)} = 0.9$

Fig. 4c: Max. $w/h \times 10^3$ for plate with $h^{(1)} / a_w^{(1)} = 0.7$

Fig. 4d: Max. $w/h \times 10^3$ for plate with $h^{(1)} / a_w^{(1)} = 0.5$

Although it can be seen from equation (9) that only elements of the D -matrix influence the calculated deflection under the current method, it is still possible to explain deflections in terms of in-plane stiffness' (which are properties of the A -matrix). This is because it can be seen from equations (2) and (3) that the A and D matrices are very closely related. A high value in the A -matrix will usually mean a high value in the corresponding D -matrix.

There is also a dependency of the terms of the D -matrix on the value of the h -parameters. These effectively position the laminate. It is therefore possible to see how in-plane stiffness terms can indirectly affect the deflection of the lamina.

Fig. 5a shows the effect of orientation on the in-plane properties of the middle lamina, layer 1. It can be seen that there is clear orthotropic behaviour, with the lowest stiffness achieved at an orientation angle of 45° . As the ratio h^1 / a_w^1 is increased, the change in shape of the weave structure causes the in-plane stiffness to drop.

Fig. 5b also shows clear orthotropic behaviour with the Bulk modulus having its highest value at an orientation of 45° . It can be seen that the value drops as the ratio h^1 / a_w^1 is increased in the same way as Fig. 5a.

Figs. 5a and 5b show a clear drop in in-plane stiffness parameters as the thickness of the middle layer is increased. The drop is attributable to increasing fibre undulation, which causes the load direction to occur along a line which is not optimal for the fibre stiffness. It should also be noted that due to the orthotropic nature of the material, the lowest stiffness occurs at an orientation angle of 45° . However, the stiffness at a load angle of 60° is not much greater. This phenomenon can explain why the greatest deflection for the various plates occurred at an orientation angle of between 45° and 60° .

The two outer laminae (Layers 2) only show change in material properties with orientation. This is because the thickness ratio of the unit cell, $h^{(2)} / a_w^{(2)}$ is fixed, as described earlier. The behaviour of the X and Y direction Young's moduli are shown in Fig. 5c. Again the lowest Young's modulus occurs at an orientation angle of between 45° and 60° for E_x .

Fig. 5a: Young's modulus vs. orientation for Layer 1

Fig. 5b: Bulk modulus vs. orientation for Layer 1

Fig. 5c: In-plane properties for Layer 2

CONCLUSIONS

The best resistance to bending is achieved when the thickness of the middle layer, $h^{(1)} / a_w^{(1)} = 0.5$. The orientation of the middle layer did not have much influence at this thickness ratio. In-plane stiffness of the laminae has a large influence on the bending stiffness of the laminate. Maximum deflection typically occurs for the laminates considered at an orientation angle of between 45^0 and 60^0 , depending on the lay-up sequence and thickness.

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